

A Comparative Study Of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Fund In Hingoli And Parbhani Districts

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Abstract:

The Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) approach has proven significant in contributing to social development. With CSR becoming mandatory, companies are making significant contributions to projects in backward areas, focusing on education, women's empowerment, healthcare and other initiatives.

Although Maharashtra receives the largest share of CSR funds. This research paper presents a comparative study of CSR funds in Hingoli and Parbhani districts of the Maharashtra state. This paper used a descriptive and analytical method.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, fund, Hingoli and Parbhani

Introduction:

According to Section 135 of the Companies Act, 2013, those companies with a net profit of 5 crore rupees or more, net worth of 500 crore rupees or more, and turnover of 1000 crore rupees or more are mandated to spend two percent of their average net profit of the preceding three years on Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) activities for social welfare. India is the first country in the world to enact such a law. Considering the CSR funds in India, the highest amount of CSR funding is utilized in Maharashtra.

Hingoli and Parbhani districts are socially, economically, and environmentally backward, facilities such as education, women's empowerment, healthcare, and water supply are limited in these districts. Therefore, to ensure the socio-economic development of such districts, companies need to allocate a greater portion of their CSR funds to these areas.

In the last five financial years, from 2019-20 to 2023-24, a certain amount of CSR funds were utilized in both these districts. However, the amount is very small. This paper analyzes this in detail.

Purpose of the study:

The purpose of the study is to analyse CSR funds comparatively in Hingoli and Parbhani districts.

Objective of the study:

1. To analyze the growth of CSR fund district wise.
2. To know the eligibility for CSR fund expenditure.
3. To compare both districts wise and year wise CSR fund.

Limitations of the study:

The present study is on maximum usage of secondary data, only limit for Hingoli and

Parbhani districts and only for five financial years. i.e. 2019-20 to 2023-24.

Furthermore, the study focuses on fund received rather than actual social impact on the ground.

Data Collection:

This study uses exclusively secondary data. The primary source of information is the National CSR data portal maintained by the Ministry of Corporate Affairs Government of India.

Geographical focus: Hingoli and Parbhani districts.

Time frame: Five years periods from financial year 2019-20 to 2023-24.

Unit of measurement: Financial figures in crore.

Literature review:

- 1) **Company act 2013:** The Companies Act 2023 sec.(135) provides information about CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility), including details on the areas where CSR funds should be invested. The act also contains rules regarding the types of companies that are required to invest in CSR funds.
- 2) **Rathod and Bhole (2024):** highlights that CSR is no longer a voluntary “goodwill” but a crucial element in corporate management. However, while law defines how much to spend, it does not mandate where to spend.
- 3) **Kavitha (2019):** observed that larger firms allocate higher CSR fund compared to small firms and expenditure pattern very across sectors. This suggest that district level CSR distribution may be influenced by the concentration of corporate headquarters.

Research Methodology:

This section outlines the systematic approach used to analyse and compare the

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) fund inflows in Hingoli and Parbhani districts. The study employs quantitative research design with a comparative approach. It focuses on numerical representation of CSR funds to identify trends, growth patterns and regional disparities between the two selected districts of Maharashtra region.

Data Analysis:

Table no.1

CSR amount received

Year	Hingoli (crore)	Parbhani (crore)
2019-20	0.13	0.15
2020-21	0.88	0.39
2021-22	2.63	1.38
2022-23	2.31	3.64
2023-24	5.34	3.4

Chart No.1

Chart No.2

Chart No.3

Finding of the Study:

- 1) Total amount received for five years in Hingoli district 11.29 Crore and Parbhani district 8.96 crore.
- 2) Table no.1 shows both districts started from very low, they have seen substantial growth though their trajectories differ.
- 3) In the financial year 2020-21 Hingoli funding jumped from 0.88 crore to 2.63 crore while Parbhani district rose 0.39 crore to 1.38 crore.
- 4) In the financial year 2022-23 the CSR fund in Hingoli district decreased from 2.63 crore to 2.31 crore while Parbhani district's CSR fund increased from 1.38 crore to 3.64 crore.
- 5) In the financial year 2023-24, the CSR fund in Hingoli district increased by almost double while Parbhani district CSR fund slightly decreased.

HDFC bank limited provided the highest amount of funding in Hingoli district. i.e. in the financial year 2020-21 0.65 crore, 2021-22 2.42 crore, in 2022-23 1.87 crore and 2023-24 2.88 crore.

In the Parbhani district **Galaxy Surfactant ltd.** gives maximum CSR fund. i.e. 1.25 crore and 0.53 crore in the financial year 2022-23 and 2023-24 respectively.

Despite the growth, the total combined funding near 8 crore is still less than 1% of what district like Pune, Mumbai receive, highlighting a massive intra-state disparity.

Conclusion:

This analysis comparing CSR funding in the Hingoli and Parbhani districts from financial year 2019-20 to 2023-24 highlights significant

shifts for the Marathwada region. The data collected demonstrates that both districts moved away from being regarded as 'CSR - neglected' areas, witnessing substantial increase in corporate investment.

Hingoli district specifically experienced an increase in funding from 0.13 crore to 5.34 crore. Although Parbhani district is more consistent compared to Hingoli district.

Lastly, the study proves regional disparity still exists.

Recommendations:

1. Most companies should utilise their CSR fund for Hingoli and Parbhani district
2. A district CSR cell should be established.
3. For holistic development, companies should implement CSR funds in other sector instead of single sector.
4. CSR projects should be designed for long-term development rather than short-term development.

References:

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